

Research Article

Enhancing Low Illumination Response of SHJ Solar Cells for More Sustainable Systems: A Device Simulation Study

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In this work, we used calibrated numerical simulation models to optimize silicon heterojunction (SHJ) solar cells, with a focus principally on higher efficiency at lower illumination. The low-light analysis is important because photovoltaic (PV) modules are exposed to varied illumination conditions depending on location, weather, and climate. Recently, we have established that for lower illumination, the SHJ configuration with thin and lower-doped front p-type emitter contact is a viable option for providing higher efficiency; however, that study was only performed for a low-doped ($\sim 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) c-Si(n) absorber. In this work, we comprehensively optimized the SHJ configuration for a wide variation of absorber doping/resistivity (5×10^{14} – $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}/9.05$ – $0.032 \Omega \text{ cm}$) and observed that for highly doped ($\sim 5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}/0.141 \Omega \text{ cm}$) absorbers, efficiency drops for thin and low-doped p-type emitters. On the contrary, a moderate to high doped (2×10^{16} – $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}/0.292$ – $0.141 \Omega \text{ cm}$) absorber with a standard p-type emitter enhances efficiency most effectively under low light illumination, where the generated carrier density is low. Additionally, a combination of a moderate to high doped absorber, together with a doped a-Si:H(p) contact layer for an optimized front electrode workfunction, further boosts efficiency irrespective of illumination. The other advantage of our optimization is the relaxed requirements of a higher work function (WF) of the front electrode necessary for a hole-selective contact in SHJ solar cells. We achieved a remarkable 3.2% absolute increase at low illumination (0.01 suns), and a 1.4% absolute increase at 0.1 and 1.0 suns compared to an STC-optimized cell (optimized experimentally for best efficiency at 1.0 sun). This analysis suggests designing PV modules providing energy production that is slightly better matched to the actual people's energy needs throughout the day and year.

Keywords: device simulation; hetero-junctions; irradiance intensity; low illumination; optimization; photovoltaic devices; silicon solar cells

1. Introduction

In the last few decades, the efficiency of silicon solar cells has been pushed by different technological and structural changes, such as passivated emitter and rear contact (PERC) [1, 2], silicon heterojunction (SHJ) [3, 4], tunnel oxide passivating contacts (TOPCon) [5, 6], and interdigitated back contact (IBC) [7, 8]. The PERC technology is approaching its efficiency limit [9, 10], and IBC technology is considered complicated and costly [11]. Recent advances in SHJ and TOPCon technologies have significantly enhanced efficiencies and are shaping the

future of the photovoltaic (PV) industry [12]. The n-type bifacial i-TOPCon technology offers a record-high efficiency of 26.58%, reported by Trinasolar [13]. Recently, for the first time, a new record efficiency of 27.08% was achieved by Trinasolar for an industrial larger-area n-type total passivation (TOPAS) solar cell, based on front and back contact heterojunction (HJT or SHJ) technology. The other competitor, Longi, breaks its record of 26.81% efficiency reported in 2023 [14] and sets a new world record of 27.09% efficiency for crystalline SHJ back-contact solar cells utilizing laser patterning techniques [15]. SHJ technology has several advantages over

TABLE 1: Parameter values adopted in simulations.

Parameters	c-Si(n)	a-Si:H(p)	a-Si:H(n)	a-Si:H(i)
Layer thickness (nm)	$0.5-2 \times 10^5$	10	10	5
Dielectric constant	11.9	11.9	11.9	11.9
Electron affinity (eV)	4.07	3.86	3.86	3.86
Band gap (eV)	1.12	1.7	1.7	1.7
N_c (cm^{-3})	2.08×10^{19}	1×10^{20}	1×10^{20}	1×10^{20}
N_v (cm^{-3})	1.04×10^{19}	1×10^{20}	1×10^{20}	1×10^{20}
Doping concentration (cm^{-3})	$5 \times 10^{14}-5 \times 10^{17}$	$5 \times 10^{18}-4 \times 10^{19}$	1×10^{21}	1×10^{14}
Defects: donors (conduction tail)	1×10^{12}	$5 \times 10^{19}-4 \times 10^{20}$	1×10^{20}	1×10^{17}
Defects: acceptors (valence tail)	1×10^{12}	$4 \times 10^{19}-3 \times 10^{20}$	1×10^{20}	1×10^{17}
Urbach E of donors (eV)	0.02	0.12	0.12	0.09
Urbach E of acceptors (eV)	0.01	0.07	0.07	0.06

FIGURE 2: (a) The comparison of thin and less doped p⁺ contact with baseline cases A and B [18]. (b) Impact of c-Si absorber doping on the efficiency of thin and low-doped a-Si:H(p) contact layer.

details of the calibrated model parameters are provided in Table 1.

We used a planar structure for our simulation instead of a textured one. The textured surface reduces reflection losses, thus slightly improving current density and consequently, efficiency. The simulation of a textured 3-D structure is time-consuming and complicated, while not altering the findings of our current investigations.

As a continuation of our recently published results [18], in which we observed that a thin and less doped a-Si:H(p) contact layer increases efficiency at low illumination for a low-doped c-Si absorber (Figure 2a). We increase the doping of the absorber while keeping thin and less doped a-Si:H(p) contact, and notice a drop in the efficiency to its baseline values at low illumination (Figure 2b), because of not having enough charges in a-Si:H(p) contact layer to compensate for the highly doped absorber. In

the next sections, we comprehensively analyze the impact of the c-Si absorber doping on cell performance.

From the experimental point of view, with varying wafer doping, one of the important parameters that must be discussed is wafer resistivity. Recently, Longi, for their world record SHJ back contact solar cells, refer to the resistivity values between 0.4 and $1.6 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$, which corresponds to a wafer doping concentration of 1.5×10^{16} – $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [15]. Liu et al. [33] have also reported wafer resistivity of 0.3 – $2.1 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$ (corresponding wafer doping of 2×10^{16} – $2.25 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) for over 25% efficiency silicon solar cells. However, for the sake of understanding, we choose a wide range of wafer doping (5×10^{14} – $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ /9.05–0.032 $\Omega \text{ cm}$). The dependance of resistivity and mobility on wafer doping is shown in Figure 3. The resistivity shows linear dependance on the c-Si (n) wafer doping; however, mobility is decreasing rapidly for higher

FIGURE 3: (a) Resistivity values for the variation of doping in n-type c-Si absorber. (b) Electron and hole mobilities.

wafer doping ($\sim 1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}/0.086 \Omega \text{ cm}$), which also reflects in the degradation of current density (Figure 4d).

As a first step, we checked the impact of c-Si doping variations on the energy band diagram at equilibrium. The simulated equilibrium band diagram shows that the overall integrated band bending equals the WF difference between the front and back electrodes (Figure 5a). Since we maintain the condition of the flat band at the back contact through a highly doped n^+ layer, the dependance of overall band bending reduces to the WF difference between the front electrode and absorber (Figure 5a); therefore, band bending occurs either in the absorber or a-Si:H(p) layer. The role of the a-Si:H(p) layer is to facilitate the extraction of holes toward the front electrode by locally inverting the absorber front surface from n-type to p-type; therefore, most of the band bending shifts inside the absorber [18]. This is important because additional band bending inside a-Si:H(p) contact layer would increase the barrier for holes above an acceptable level ($\sim 0.55 \text{ eV}$, refer to our previous paper [29]). Therefore, an increase in the n-type doping of the absorber above a certain level may also increase the requirements on the level of a-Si:H(p) layer doping. Since the doping in the absorber shifts the electron quasi-Fermi level (QFL) and reduces WF, thus in most cases of moderate doping, the increase in absorber n-type doping will reduce the requirements of higher electrode WF for hole selective contacts in SHJ solar cells.

In our previously published works [29, 34], we defined contact strength (the ability of a contact to efficiently collect the photo-generated carriers through electrode WF or a-Si:H(p) contact layer doping/thickness, or a combination of both, for a given illumination). We investigated these requirements and their relaxation for lower irradiance for a low-doped absorber ($1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Usually, going above the required level of contact strength (5.19 eV for hole selective contacts, equivalent to the valence band energy of c-Si) is not beneficial

for cell performance. In our recent analysis [18], we noticed that reducing the contact strength can increase efficiency at low irradiances, only for low-doped absorbers ($1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}/4.594 \Omega \text{ cm}$), as shown in Figure 2a. The question remains what happens in the case of higher absorber doping. First, due to the strong dependance of the electron QF level on absorber doping and only weak dependance of the hole QF level results in an overall larger QFL splitting (QFLS) (Figure 5b). The QFLS was calculated 10 nm deep from the surface of the c-Si absorber. We evaluated ideality factor (n) as a slope of QFLS vs. the logarithm of illumination (Figure 5b) and noticed that the baseline device (full lines) operates mostly in the regime of $n = 1.5$ (highlighted by blue), while the highly doped device operates in the regime of $n = 1$.

3. Optimization at Low Illuminations

To deeply analyze the impact of c-Si doping on the SHJ cell performance, short circuit current density (J_{SC}), open circuit voltage (V_{OC}), fill factor (FF), and cell efficiency were extracted from device simulation (Figure 4) and compared with the technological baseline (experimental data [29]). At STC, the V_{OC} , which depends on the QFLS in the absorber, slightly decreases with increasing absorber doping (Figure 4a); however, at low illumination (0.01 suns), where the generated carrier density is low, the trend is the opposite, and V_{OC} gradually and slowly improves. At high doping ($> 1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}/0.086 \Omega \text{ cm}$), V_{OC} at all illumination levels starts dropping because a-Si:H(p) layer is not anymore able to provide enough charge to keep the band bending in the absorber and, consequently, the barrier for holes ϕ (Figure 5a) becomes larger than 0.55 eV, which is the value where the extracted voltage become limited [29]. Apart from this extreme case, the trends in V_{OC} can be described by the concept of the ideality factor, and we know that the theoretical optimum is $n = 1$. We try to get the ideality factor as close to 1

FIGURE 4: The impact of c-Si doping variation on (a) open circuit voltage (V_{OC}), (b) FF, (c) efficiency, and (d) short circuit current density. a-Si:H(p) layer doping and front electrode WF are fixed to 1×10^{19} cm $^{-3}$ and 5.1 eV, respectively.

(minimize recombination) using the variation of c-Si doping (Figure 5b) and evaluate it from the voltage at the maximum power point V_{MPP} . The FF, on the other hand, increases with increasing c-Si doping, more strongly at lower illumination because the impact of series resistance becomes negligible. Note that (Figure 4c) by just optimizing absorber doping, we can boost >2% efficiency at 0.01 suns (18.4% compared to

16%), 0.6% at 0.1 suns (20.55% compared to 19.95%), and 0.4% at 1.0 sun (22.7% compared to 22.3%). A large portion of this improvement in efficiency comes from the FF.

To better understand it, we plot the excess carrier density as a function of depth for various absorber dopings. The increase in c-Si absorber doping modified the carrier density close to its interface (Figure 6a) as compared to the bulk (Figure 6b)

FIGURE 5: (a) Simulated equilibrium band diagram of the a-Si:H(p)/a-Si:H(i)/c-Si(n) interface for doping variation in the c-Si absorber. (b) Simulated positions of quasi-Fermi levels (extracted 10 nm below the top surface of c-Si absorber) with varying illumination intensity; the slopes of the lines correspond to ideality factor $n \approx 1$, except for the sections indicated by blue bars with $n \approx 1.5$.

FIGURE 6: Excess electron and hole concentration at maximum power point (MPP) for different doping concentrations of c-Si absorber. (a) Zoom view and (b) full-scale view.

because of induced band bending by the WF difference between the doped a-Si:H(p)/electrode and c-Si absorber. For the low-doped (\sim intrinsic) absorber, the maximum band bending is defined by the mid-gap energy of the bandgap of the c-Si absorber, that is, 0.56 eV, and is reached for the highest a-Si:H (p) doping/WF of the electrode. This is not the case for doped absorbers. The fundamental rule is that band bending is either

provided by the electrode WF/doped a-Si:H(p) layer or a combination of both. For doped absorbers (n-type), the Fermi level moves close to the conduction band, thus relaxing the requirement of strong doping in the a-Si:H(p) layer or higher WF materials for the electrode. With increasing c-Si(n) doping, the excess hole (minority carrier) concentration decreases (Figure 6a,b), thus increasing the minority carrier lifetime/

FIGURE 7: Showing the impact of c-Si thickness on (a) short circuit current density: at 0.01 suns, we multiplied it by 100 to make it comparable to 1.0 sun illumination, (b) open circuit voltage, (c) fill factor, and (d) efficiency. a-Si:H(p) layer doping and front electrode WF are fixed to $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and 5.1 eV, respectively.

diffusion length, which results in enhancing the cell efficiency. This is valid until the excess carrier concentration remains higher than the doping of the c-Si absorber. Further increasing the doping ($\sim 5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3} / 0.032 \Omega \text{ cm}$) of the c-Si absorber reduces the generated current density, thus efficiency, irrespective of illumination (Figure 4c,d). This is because of the accumulation of electrons close to the a-Si:H(i)/c-Si(n) interface (Figure 6), thus limiting the movement of generated holes toward the a-Si:H(p) layer, which results in reducing short

circuit current density (Figure 4d). Another factor contributing to the degradation of current density is the steep degradation of mobility of minority carriers (Figure 3b).

We have also analyzed the impact of c-Si absorber thickness (Figure 7) and noticed that for a low-doped absorber ($\sim 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} / 4.594 \Omega \text{ cm}$), reducing the c-Si thickness reduces efficiency at 1.0 sun and marginally improves it at 0.01 suns. This reduction at 1.0 sun mainly comes from the current reduction for thinner absorbers (optical losses, Figure 7a). The voltage and FF slightly

FIGURE 8: The impact of a-Si:H(p) layer doping and absorber doping on the efficiency of SHJ solar cell (a) 0.01 suns, (b) 0.1 suns, and (c) 1.0 sun. The experimental data corresponds to a-Si(p) doping: $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, front electrode WF: 5.1 eV, c-Si doping: $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, c-Si thickness: 200 μm .

improve with reduced absorber thickness (Figure 7b,c). We compared the most promising c-Si doping cases (2×10^{16} and $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) with the baseline case. For a moderately doped ($2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}/0.292 \Omega \text{ cm}$) absorber, efficiency increases to 18.2%, 20.3%, and 22.7% compared to the technological baseline (16%, 19.95%, and 22.3%) at 0.01, 0.1, and 1.0 sun, respectively (Figure 7d). For a $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ absorber doping case, efficiency further enhanced to 18.4%, and 20.55% at 0.01 and 0.1 suns, respectively, while unaffected at 1.0 sun.

Furthermore, we vary the a-Si:H(p) contact layer doping and examine the impact of both c-Si doping and illumination on cell

performance (Figure 8). For the efficient collection of holes, we require a WF equal to the valence band energy of the c-Si absorber ($\sim 5.19 \text{ eV}$). With the a-Si: H(p) doping of $2 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which is well within the experimental limits [35], we noticed a substantial gain in the efficiency (M 2%) at low illumination (0.01 suns). For further increasing a-Si:H(p) doping (M $2 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), which corresponds to the higher WF compared to 5.19 eV, the impact of a-Si:H(p) doping, irrespective of illumination, ceases to exist. This is because at very high doping in a-Si:H (p), all the dopant atoms are compensated by the dangling bonds, leading to a pinning of the Fermi level and thus to the

FIGURE 9: The impact of front electrode work function, a-Si:H(p) contact layer doping and absorber doping on the efficiency (a) 0.01 suns, (b) 0.1 suns, and (c) 1.0 sun. The symbol only represents experimental data.

saturation of the conductivity. It is fascinating that at 1.0 sun illumination, the impact of both c-Si doping and a-Si:H(p) doping is small, in comparison to the impact at lower illumination (0.01 suns). The higher doping in the absorber facilitates maintaining higher doping in the a-Si:H(p) contact layer due to charge balance at the a-Si:H(i)/c-Si(n) interface. Furthermore, in the case of low illumination where carrier generation is low, higher doping boosts the voltage together with a considerable gain in FF (not shown here), thus improving efficiency. It is quite clear that optimizing these structural parameters is relatively important for low illumination. Using our comprehensive optimization approach, we achieved a notable 3.2 % absolute

increase in efficiency at 0.01 suns, and 1.4% absolute increase at 0.1 and 1.0 suns, compared to baseline efficiency (Figure 8).

Finally, the variation in efficiency with front electrode WF is shown in Figure 9. For lower a-Si:H(p) doping, the electrode WF has a strong influence, specifically at 1.0 sun illumination. The increase in absorber doping only improves efficiency at lower illumination; however, the higher doping in the a-Si:H(p) layer, together with higher doping in the absorber, increases the efficiency irrespective of illumination and electrode WF. The requirement of a higher WF is relaxed at lower illumination for hole-selective contacts in SHJ solar cells.

4. Conclusions

The lower-doped and thin contacts are usually good for improving efficiency at low illumination; however, this is valid in the case of the lower-doped absorber ($1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The present study demonstrates that experimentally feasible moderate doping ($2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}/0.292 \Omega \text{ cm}$) in the absorber boosts cell efficiency by >2% absolute under low light illumination (0.01 suns) while also slightly (0.35%) enhancing it at STC in comparison to the baseline efficiency. Once the doping in the (n)c-Si absorber is increased, higher doping in the a-Si:H(p) layer is required to maintain charge balance at a-Si:H(i)/c-Si interface. The combination of higher doping in the a-Si:H(p) layer with moderate to high doping in the (n)c-Si absorber for an optimized WF of the front electrode can provide a substantial gain in efficiency overall, but intensely under low light conditions. The requirement of a higher WF is further relaxed in the case of well-optimized doping of a-Si:H(p) contact layer. We achieved an outstanding 3.2% absolute gain in efficiency at 0.01 suns, and 1.4% absolute improvement both at 0.1 and 1.0 suns, compared to the baseline device. The current optimization approach helps to improve the total energy yield of modules based on the SHJ solar cell technology in countries where the average irradiance level is below average.

Data Availability Statement

The data will be available upon request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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